

NEWSLETTER

Green and Sustainable Processes for Electrode Production

WELCOME!

Our first newsletter is finally here. Thank you for finding your way to our project and our newsletter.

After 18 months of greenSPEED, we thought that it is time to give you a short recap of the first activities. In this volume, you will find out more about our first face to face meetings, the progress we made so far and what we plan in the next months.

We hope you enjoy this volume!

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INTRODUCING THE greenSPEED PROJECT

About greenSPEED

greenSPEED is an EU-funded research project aiming to revolutionise battery production in Europe. By reducing energy consumption, lowering the carbon footprint achieving ZERO emissions of Volatile Organic Compounds (VOCs), and therefore reducing costs, greenSPEED is leading the way towards a more sustainable future for battery cells. On our way to support achieving European leadership in battery production, greenSPEED is tackling the following challenges:

greenSPEED Key Facts

Project Duration: 1. July 2022 – 31. December 2025 (42 Months)

Consortium: 11 Partners, 5 Countries

Project Budget: 5,3 Mio. EUR

Funded under Horizon Europe: HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-04

Coordinated by: Virtual Vehicle Research GmbH

The greenSPEED Consortium

OUR FACE TO FACE MEETINGS

KICK-OFF MEETING

05. - 06. July 2022 | Graz, Austria

In July last year, we met to kick off the project and used the time for presentations, exciting discussions and a social event to further refine the vision of greenSPEED.

[Read More](#)

FIRST GENERAL ASSEMBLY

25. - 26. January 2023 | Lyon, France

We came together in the beautiful city of Lyon, hosted by Arkema and used the time to recap the 6 months and discuss upcoming activities and important project milestones.

[Read More](#)

SECOND GENERAL ASSEMBLY

28. - 29. June 2023 | Eindhoven, Netherlands

Hosted by LeydenJar Technologies, we met for the 2nd GA and shared insights, celebrated achievements, and laid out future plans.

[Read More](#)

SUMMARY FIRST 18 MONTHS

Main Achievements

The main achievements from the first 18 project months can be summarised as follows:

- Definition of automotive requirement for our central project result: the greenSPEED battery cell
- Definition of anode formulation with a high silicon content and innovative binder materials
- Progress review in setting up VOC free dry coating process for the cathode
- Work towards digitalisation of battery production process by accessing machine data as input for machine learning algorithms
- The partners have worked to improve the sustainability of electrode materials and to address the challenges of performance, efficiency and scalability.
 - Key topics included material definitions, tuning and optimising parameters in new processing steps, creating a first cell generation and extrapolating future impact.
- All the specifications for our cell were defined, which provided the necessary framework for our teamwork.
- From an anode processing perspective, two strategies were chosen: a dry and a water-based one.
 - The base components are optimised for these different processing techniques. And the later pre-lithiation process is also emphasised.
 - The cathode material for dry processing is characterised and first sample electrodes are produced with satisfactory results.
- A first generation of greenSPEED cells will be built based on the results of the first year of the project. The supporting topics, modelling of the cell components and setting up the framework for production cost evaluation and sustainability, are ongoing. The challenge here is clearly to provide the necessary information in time for the later decisions.

OUR PUBLIC DELIVERABLES

The first 4 public greenSPEED Deliverables are available for download:

- D7.1 greenSPEED Quality Assurance and Risk Management Plan
- D7.2 greenSPEED Initial Data Management Plan
- D7.3 greenSPEED Project Identity and Web Presence
- D7.4 greenSPEED Preliminary Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

[Find out more](#)

DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

The Battery Heroes

Together with our sister projects from the same call (HORIZON-CL5-2021-D2-01-04), we have created the Battery Heroes: a cluster to consolidate our collaboration. We aim to combine efforts, maximise our impact, exchange knowledge, share information on similar challenges and facilitate networking with stakeholders to ultimately ensure visibility. We have also welcomed two new projects: BATMACHINE and GIGABAT!

greenSPEED EU Project: Innovating Battery Production for a Greener Tomorrow

Official greenSPEED Project Video

greenSPEED Project Video

In our first project year, we shared our official project video, introducing how we plan to innovate Europe's battery production for a greener tomorrow.

 [You can watch it here.](#)

greenSPEED at UECT 2023

Organised by our project partner ZSW, the Ulm Electrochemical Talks celebrated its 30th anniversary with more than 300 participants.

Our project partner Dr. Thomas Wöhrle from BMW presented the greenSPEED project during his presentation "Battery-Cell Technology

Development at BMW". Jonas Neumeyer from ZSW presented a poster during the conference. The poster outlined the "solvent-free processing of cathodes for high-energy lithium ion batteries". The poster is available for download [here](#).

greenSPEED presented at UECT 2023

greenSPEED presented at EARPA FORM FORUM

greenSPEED at EARPA FORM FORUM

Virtual Vehicle took the opportunity to host a booth at the EARPA Form Forum in Brussels and presented the greenSPEED project to an international audience. They also used the opportunity to introduce the Battery Heroes.

COMING UP

Stay tuned for:

Events, Conferences & Meetings

RTR Conference
5. – 7. February 2024

Review Meeting
29. February 2024

Transport Research Arena (TRA)
15. – 18. April 2024

EARPA FORM Forum
30. September – 1. October 2024

Batteries Event
16. – 18. October 2024

Future Battery Forum
Berlin + Online

Future Battery Forum
5. – 6. November 2024

Battery Experts Forum
5. – 7. November 2024

Ulm Electrochemical Talks
4. – 5. June 2025

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